
Bagging Deep Q-Networks by Clusters of GPUs

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Abstract

We present synchronous GPU clusters of independently-trained deep Q-networks (DQNs), which are bootstrap aggregated (“bagged”) for action selection in games on Atari 2600. Our work is an extension of code based on Torch in LuaJIT from Google DeepMind on February 26, 2015 [1,2]. We heavily used Amazon Web Services g2.2xlarge GPUs for processing 100s of GBs across 100s of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with 100,000s of CUDA cores for 100s of hours; and we used m3.2xlarge SSDs with high i/o for master orchestration of CNN slaves. To scale our bagging architecture [3], we built on the high performance computing framework CfnCluster-0.0.20 from AWS Labs [4].

We tested architectures of up to 18 GPUs for playing 2 games. We followed Dean *et al.*’s “warmstarting” of large-scale deep neural networks [5] to radically constrain the global space of exploration by asynchronous learners. This meant pre-training a “parent” network for 24 hours, and then using its parameters to initialize weights for “children” networks, which were trained 36 hours further, without any communication of weight gradients to each other.

Thus far, the “warmstart” technique for constraining exploration of asynchronous learner has been too effective. The children DQNs learn enormously beyond their parents - nearly 4x improvement in average score - but all of their learnings are about identical: at any given point in time, ensembles of 1, 3, 6, 12, and 18 DQNs always average out to the same actions, because together the children believe the same things. This suggests that we should experiment with the following calibrations: (i) pre-train “parents” of the warmstart for less time, (ii) increase learning rates of “children”, and (iii) increase probability of greedy- ϵ exploration by “children”. These will diverge asynchronous learners to support discovery of unique features in training. Experiments are in process to validate this and our framework for large-scale deep reinforcement learning.

1 Introduction

Q-learning is a model-free reinforcement learning algorithm for finding an optimal action-selection policy in a reward-driven environment [6]. A q-learning algorithm is generally too computationally expensive to implement on raw data, so often linear approximators reduce the dimensionality of input space, but many important features of the data are often lost in this process. Recently, deep Q-networks (DQNs) were introduced to solve the problem of intelligent dimensionality reduction of the input data, based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [2]. A DQN approximates an optimal action-value function using $Q^*(s, a)$, which is defined as follows:

$$Q^*(s, a) = \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E} [r_t + \gamma r_{t+1} + \gamma^2 r_{t+2} + \dots | s_t = s, a_t = a, \pi]$$

For an input state s_t at time t , the above term is maximized when the expected sum of estimated future rewards r_{t+i} is maximized, where rewards further into the future are exponentially discounted

in value by a factor γ (e.g. 0.9). One of the innovations of the DQN framework is that the action-value selector is approximated by weight parameters θ of a neural network with a linear rectifier output: $Q(s, a; \theta) \approx Q^*(s, a)$. This opens up the problem to broad solutions in deep learning research, including the application of CNNs, which have been used to dramatically increase accuracy of machine learning tasks in recent years; they are a natural fit as a state-space function approximator of raw image data, which must be pre-processed in reinforcement learning applications like q-networks [7,8,9,10,11].

In the DQN architecture introduced by Mnih *et al.* [2], images of the screen displayed in an Atari video game are collected from the Arcade Learning Environment (ALE) [12]; the network then processes each image, and outputs an action that is sent back to the ALE game agent. For the network to select an action, the raw image is first linearly downsampled from 210 X 160 pixels to 84 X 84 pixels. Then it is processed by a CNN with 3 layers, followed by 2 fully connected linear rectifier layers, the last layer which outputs one of 18 possible actions that an Atari agent can do.

Our contribution is to scale up this framework to benefit from large-scale distributed computing, based on research showing that voting among ensembles of independent machine learning models - also known as bootstrap aggregation, or “bagging” - generally improves the performance and stability of statistical classifiers like deep networks [5,13,14,15].

Engineering of DQN Ensembles on GPU Clusters

To build GPU clusters for bagging ensembles of DQNs, we use GPU machines (“G2 instances”) from Amazon Web Services [16]. Each instance provides up to 1,536 CUDA cores and 4 GB of video memory, as well as at least 8 CPUs with 60 GB of SSD memory. We implemented NVIDIA drivers to set up the “machine image” (*i.e.* development environment) for GPU computing [17]. Ultimately, as we allocated DQNs on GPUs of the same parameters as by Mnih *et al.* [2], we found that we could safely put 2 isolated DQNs on the same GPU, without (too often) encountering memory access issues. To enable a master to quickly orchestrate connections across all DQNs, we customized an instance (“m3.2xlarge”) with an SSD drive capable of input and output of data at up to 30X the number of data allocated (24 GB): 720 i/o per second. This was important, in addition to placing all machines in the same subnet, which helped to ensure they were as physically close together as possible, and thus minimize latency. To coordinate all of this in a secure and robust way, we turned to the open source framework being designed by AWS Labs specifically for high performance cluster computing on their services, CfnCluster-0.0.20 [4]. We find this framework to be a promising even if young infrastructure to build upon.

With computing infrastructure ready, we ultimately turned to code that Google DeepMind released for “academic evaluation” on February 26, 2015 [18]. Our current architecture built around this code can be found on GitHub [3]. As required by the license for using this code, our application and disclosure of our work relating to it is only for academic evaluation. Meanwhile, we find no strong open source framework for cluster computing of deep networks specifically, so we take a first step in releasing a general architecture that may eventually benefit the deep learning R&D community.

Code for the DQN was written in the scientific computing framework called Torch in LuaJIT [1]. The use of Torch versus, *e.g.* Theano, is a choice that generally makes sense for a deep learning researcher in pursuit of the fastest run times. It was shown for the same computations that Torch is faster than Theano sometimes by double or triple the speed; and increasingly so, for increasingly larger training set sizes that must be processed [1]. This is mainly because Python has many “inefficiencies” in memory management, including in Theano [19], which were designed to ease application development; meanwhile, Torch is based on LuaJIT which is a minimalist wrapper around a C compiler, run in a “just in time” fashion for versatile and efficient extensibility across platforms.

However, we discovered that using LuaJIT comes at the cost of very limited documentation and maturity of libraries. In our particular case, we ultimately needed to severely constrain the scalability of our current architecture, because of a lack of mature/effective libraries in LuaJIT for implementing true multi-threading of dynamically generated data. This trade-off forces our master controller to *sequentially* query slaves for their action vote, instead doing this in a truly parallel way. This is a top priority for us to address in ensuing work, because this constraint breaks the real-time gameplay of the DQNs for networks too large. In our currently limited architecture, run-time grows linearly with number of DQNs, instead of, *e.g.*, logarithmically.

Figure 1: Architecture for Bagging Deep Q-Networks

The high-level abstraction for how our ensemble architecture works is described in Figure 1. After training several DQNs, we synchronize their beliefs, across a cluster of computers. The basic idea is

to have a single master agent playing an Atari 2600 game, which is responsible for actually inputting the next action to ALE, and getting the next state (image) from ALE. After every state, the master first does the preprocessing of reducing it down to 84 X 84 pixels, and then sends that image out to all of its “slaves”. Each of the slaves is a unique DQN with a unique set of weight parameters. When a slave receives an image, it forward propagates it through its CNN and fully-connected linear rectifier units, to output its belief of what the “best” action is. Then it sends this action belief back to the master, which collects all suggested actions from all of the DQNs. In our current architecture, the master simply does a majority vote to choose the most popular action. The testing process repeats for a fixed number of frames, and the score after each frame is recorded to see how the ensemble performs across a large number of episodes.

We followed Dean *et al.*'s “warmstarting” of large-scale deep neural networks [5] to radically constrain the global space of exploration by asynchronous learners. This meant pre-training a “parent” network for 24 hours, and then using its parameters to initialize weights for “children” networks, which were trained 36 hours further, without any communication of weight gradients to each other.

Figure 2: Evidence of Learning by “Children” Deep Q-Networks

Table 1: Solidarity of Vote: Probability of Identical Vote Per Action

Number of Networks Voting / Game	Breakout	PacMan
6 networks	92%	99%
12 networks	96%	100%
18 networks	93%	98%

Table 2: Independent DQNs Learn Approximately Identical Features

Number of DQNs Tested as Ensemble After 60 Hours of Training	Breakout	PacMan
1 network	39.48	74.09
3 networks	39.48	74.09
6 networks	39.48	74.09
12 networks	39.48	74.09
18 networks	39.48	74.09

Results and Conclusions

We tested architectures of up to 18 GPUs for playing 2 games. Thus far, the “warmstart” technique for constraining exploration of asynchronous learner has been too effective. The children DQNs learn enormously beyond their parents - nearly 4x improvement in average score, as seen in Figure 2 - but all of their learnings are about identical, as shown in Tables 1 and 2: at any given point in time, ensembles of 1, 3, 6, 12, and 18 DQNs always average out to the same actions, because together the children approximately believe the same things. We do see that there is slightly more divergence in one game (Breakout) than another (PacMan), which suggests that it may be difficult but interesting to tune parameters for encouraging enough divergence to learn useful features across games. To do this, we are now exploring the following parameter changes in experiments with results forthcoming: (i) pre-train “parents” of the warmstart for less time, (ii) increase learning rates of “children”, and (iii) increase probability of greedy- ϵ exploration by “children”. These will diverge asynchronous learners to support discovery of unique features in training, and it will be very interesting to find explore different mixes of explorativeness.

We have also invested substantial time in improving model parallelism across GPUs, and on a smarter dynamic programming of the greedy- ϵ exploration (rather than a simple linear annealing), and we remain hopeful for future results in both areas.

Meanwhile, we aim to formalize our framework for large-scale deep reinforcement learning in the coming months of experiments. In particular, we intend to engineer an open source library for cluster computing of deep neural networks, which will initially be focused on supporting our reinforcement learning application, but ideally be designed to support the deep learning community as a whole.

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